

Literature as a tool to demystify societal norms and values in the contemporary African society: A critique of the African patriarchal system in Buchi Emecheta's *Second Class Citizen*

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Abstract

The novel, "Second Class Citizen" by Buchi Emecheta brings to lime light the ills in the African patriarchal leadership using the custom and culture of Ibozo community in Eastern Nigeria to expose the discrimination, dehumanization and segregation placed on females (girl-children and women) in the African society. The novel is anchored on Wollstonecraft (1792) theory of feminism titled, "A vindication of the rights of women" which states that women are not naturally inferior to men and should be given opportunity to get educated like men so as to serve the society equally. The theorist frowns at the convictions that, women are forced to focus solely on trivial accomplishments that would make them a better wife and mother to the small unit of the family rather than anything important in the society. The theorist also frowns at an educational system that deliberately trains women to be frivolous and incapable of making impact in the society. Thus, the theorist admonishes those women and men alike are depicted as rational beings that can be excellent workers in politics and other professions. The novelist is thematically pre-occupied with men's unfaithfulness in marriage, societal limitation and subjugation on a female child, parental interference in marital affairs, societal stratification, social constraints and custom, dehumanization and untimely death. This paper therefore addresses the wrong notion men in African society have on girl child that she is less important in the society. It further condemns African patriarchal system and advocates for women equality, girl child education, women participation in politics and involvement in diverse areas of endeavors.

Key words: discrimination, subjugation, emancipation, dehumanization, segregation, patriarchal.

Introduction

Emecheta's novel, "Second Class Citizen" (as anchored on Wollstonecraft feminist theory, 1792) exposes the ills of the African patriarchy society in which women are insignificant but are compelled to work round the clock to enhance societal development. The Igbos of Eastern - Nigeria are hugely represented in this work while the setting is in Lagos (Southern - Nigeria). The novelist uses the heroine, a little girl called Adah who is just eight years old to highlight the salient features of a system that is against women achievement and existence. These include discrimination, dehumanization, subjugation of female, men's unfaithfulness in marriage, parental influence in marital affairs, social constraints and custom, slavery, sexual molestation and untimely death.

The novel opens with the protagonist, Adah, a little girl of eight years whose birth was not recorded at the hospital because she was a girl and therefore, insignificant to her family and community. Adah's hope to further her education is dashed down with the death of her father "Pa" who knew the importance of educating a girl. Her mother "Ma" has a contrary view alongside with other members of the family that she needs only elementary education to be able to read, write and acquire numeracy skills as a girl-child. All the family income is kept to sponsor "Boy," her younger brother to higher school.

Adah experiences discrimination and dehumanization right from birth. Adah was "a disappointment" to her parents, immediate family, and tribe. She was so insignificantly born such that her birth was not recorded. However, she was born during the Second World War so events surrounding that period hinted she is eight **p.7"**

Adah struggles to pay her common Entrance Examination fees through an illegal means from the money that was meant to buy meat which she hid underground. Adah is determined to suffer the pain of 103 strokes of cane from her maternal-cousin; she sees herself as a martyr. She performs exceptionally in her first term in the college and is given scholarship that span across all her years of study in Methodist Girls School. After graduating from college, what is glaring is Adah's marriage which hangs on Adah like "the sword of Damocles". She goes against the wish of her mother "Ma" and other family members to marry 'Francis' a young accountant who is aspiring to become a chartered accountant but fails most of his accountancy courses in London. Her family rather wants her to marry one of the rich old men (old baldies - as she popularly called them) asking for her hand in marriage. Her family ex-communicates her, nobody attends her wedding, even Boy, her only brother; only her mother-in-law and her husband's family are in attendance. She gives birth to her first daughter, Titi. The same day her mother dies (at age 38) while still in the hospital. Boy and others do not visit her when she gives birth.

Adah gets a highly paid job as a Librarian with the American Consulate Library Lagos. She uses her juicy salary for her husband and his people to the negligence of her mother and Boy. Adah eventually regrets

her action of negligence only after her mother dies and she realizes she had not done a single thing for her. She sends her husband abroad to study accountancy and sends her 20pounds monthly with the belief that she would soon realize her dream of going to England to join him. She uses her salary to pay school fees of husband's seven sisters, family's house rent, pay her four housemaids, feed other members of the household including herself and the children.

When she finally makes up her mind to leave her highly paid job and join Francis in England, she has to plead and bribe her mother-in-law along with other family members using money and lots of gifts to be permitted to join her husband. Adah only sees Boy the day she is leaving Nigeria for England, she misses him greatly. On arrival, Adah and her two children, Titi and Vicky are faced with a grim situation. Her husband is in a ghetto (place meant for blacks and coloured) in a half-size room with one cushion chair without space.

Adah meets a religious husband who is hostile, brutal and commanding. Francis rejects the idea of birth control. In a twinkle of an eye, Adah gets pregnant despite the fact that the situation demands she gets a job immediately in order to survive with a student-husband. Being a prayerful wife she struggles to get a job and is offered one at North Finchley library.

Adah almost loses her son, Vicky, through Trudy's man-handling. Trudy is a white woman keeping a foster home who is also a side-chick to Francis (All blacks are compelled to keep their children in foster homes and pay heavily). When Adah gives birth to her third child, she loses her job at Finchley Library because of childbirth.

As a struggling woman she gets another job, this time at Chalkfarm Library. She uses her time judiciously and is able to write a manuscript of her first novel. It seems hilarious to her but her two friends and colleagues, Bill and Peggy whom she met at her place of work perceive it as "A brain child" of Adah and "A delight to the society" respectively (pp. 186-187). Adah is encouraged and enthused but unfortunately, it turns out that Francis finds the manuscript in her belongings and burns it in her absence, condemning it as an act meant for men and not women who are Second-Class Citizens.

This acts as the last straw that breaks the camel's back. Adah packs her things out of Francis house to stay on her own though she is pregnant for the fourth child. Against all odds she decides to further her education, train her children in school and give them a sound upbringing. She makes up her mind to face life as a Second-Class citizen. Adah makes herself a symbol of strength, freedom, success and dignity for womanhood.

Theoretical framework

This paper is anchored on Mary Wollstonecraft (1792) theory of feminism titled: A vindication of the rights of women. The theory propagates that women are not born inferior to men but are put into that position because they lack education. It suggests that both men and women be treated as rational beings and imagines a social order founded on reason devoid of gender. Wollstonecraft attests that women education is very important because men and women, adult and children, family, and marriage would all benefit from greater opportunities given to women. The theorist frowns at the educational system that trains women to be frivolous, trivial and incapable of focusing on accomplishments that would make them better, rather the education is meant to make them wives to serve men only. Women are supposed to be trained to become politically and professionally inclined in addition to being good mothers and wives. The theory further advocates that, radical reforms are required to adjust the patriarchal system which is the main cause of gender inequality and gender stereotypes. Women are subordinates because men assume more power. A society where all the secret rights of humanity are violated because a portion of society cherishes blind obedience will not gain great advancement.

In the same vein Sankera (1987) opined that there is no true social revolution without the liberation of women and that no revolution would be able to triumph without the emancipation of women. The author argues that women began to suffer when society transitioned from a matriarchal to patriarchal system. Sankera rebukes "Locker- room men" who did not allow their wives to participate in politics; he advocates that men should take up household task alongside their wives. The author sees the emancipation of women transcending the systems of exploitation, stereotypical gender roles, prostitution and many more, bringing restoration to the true image of society (Sankera, 1987). This is evident in the fact that from creation women were placed in charge of giving birth and grooming (*Genesis 3: 20*) lives in society which goes a long way to explain that only sound minds could be entrusted to bring- up sound human beings, so societal advancement and progress is largely dependent on women liberation and emancipation. The crux of the matter is that the society that relies solely on the patriarchal system is likely to experience stagnation.

Wollstonecraft theory has a direct link to Emecheta's (1977) novel titled: *Second-Class Citizen*. This literary work exposes the ills and status of the patriarchal society over feminism. It portrays a society where a girl - child (woman) is not supposed to be educated; rather she is to be prolific and dutiful for the benefit of the family, community and society. The theory propagates the ills against women and the resultant discrimination and limitations on women in society.

One could obviously see that Adah resumes the responsibility of a grown up woman at the tender age of 8 years. She is woken up at 4.30 am to fetch water at the pump many yards away from home, at least 10 to 12 times to fill a big jar for the day and to fix things up for her uncle who goes to work at 6.30 am. These along with many other house chores are what she is subjected to in her uncle's house, after the death of

her father. At age 12, she is asked to start a family business in order to raise money for her uncle's family. Adah is perplexed with the thought of raising money for a big family of 9.

When her father, Pa dies she is separated from her mother, Ma and her younger brother, Boy, who is the only one to be trained in a good school and also benefit from the father's inheritance. Her mother and the rest of the family members do not believe in a girl's education except her father, Pa who died. Adah goes through primary and secondary schools by her strong will. She pays for her Common Entrance Examination through a dubious means as the only alternative. She hides the 2 pounds her uncle sent her to buy meat with and is determined to suffer 103 strokes of cane from her maternal cousin to be able to pay for her Common Entrance.

After Adah's graduation from secondary school she has no option than to marry. Adah marries poor Francis Obi against the wish of her people who wants her to marry a rich old man. She gets a highly paid job with the American Consulate Library. Francis turns Adah into a money and baby-making factory. She sponsors Francis abroad to study accounting in London, his seven sisters in school and takes care of his parents and whole family to the negligence of her own family. She only realizes this when her mother dies of frustration and insatiable life at the age of 38, in the house of Pa's elder brother who inherited her.

The novelist presents to the readers the African patriarchal society that view women as property that can be inherited and misused. Ma, Adah's mother is inherited by her husband's brother at the demise of her husband. Adah hates her mother's predicament but cannot help it as a child. She later thought it would have been better if she married one of the rich "old baldies" to have afforded bringing her mother and Boy to stay with her. Adah herself is inherited by her mother's brother as a servant in a house that has four big boys, she is the only one who wakes up at 4.30 am to do all the house chores and fix things for her uncle before he goes to work by 6.30 am (p.19).

She serves a family of nine alone and at the age of 12 she is already contributing financially to the family. This form of subjugation and dehumanization is explained by the Igbo custom as, training up a girl to be strong and responsible as a future wife.

Textual Analysis

The novel is critically analysed based on the following subheadings:

- i. Men's unfaithfulness in marriage.
- ii. Societal stratification, social constraints and custom.
- iii. Parental interference in marital affairs.

iv. Dehumanization and Sudden Death.

v. Educational implications.

Men's unfaithfulness in marriage

Adah experiences subjugation, dehumanization and segregation from her husband, Francis and his family. She is used as a money and baby - making machine for Francis and his family when she gets a juicy job as a librarian at the American Consulate Library. She has to train her husband to read accounting in London, pay school fees of his seven sisters, pay rent for the family house, carter for herself and children and pay for the services of her four housemaids to the negligence of her family. Adah regrets the fact that she had not been of help to her mother, only when she hears of her death. Adah allows herself to be cheated by her father-in-law who uses a 'hate speech' which makes her believe that nobody loves her from her father's house since she wedded and gave birth to her first child, Titi and none of them has come to attend the wedding nor visit her. Despite her intelligence, she allows her senses to be tamed by men's betrayal.

Adah's husband refuses to work claiming to be a student who is too busy to do business meanwhile he denies her from having birth control to the detriment of her health using religion as a cover. According to Jehovah Witness "birth control" is a sin. Three weeks after Adah survived the birth of her third child, Bubu, through a caesarean section, Francis beats Adah mercilessly because she opted for birth control. "Adah's head throbs and feels dizzy with pain; her mouth bleeds (P.160). Francis and his people conclude that she wants birth control so that she could easily have affair with other men behind his back (P.160). He prescribes a crude way of birth control whereby "you pour on the floor" during love making (P.161).

In a typical African society men marry because of procreation. They are not responsible for the upkeep of their family. It does not matter if the wife dies of child birth. Francis Obi is a figurative example of those who see their wives as "second class citizens," who should be sex object, bearing them children, being slept with anytime, work for them, taking their beatings and listening to their Jehovah Witness sermons (P.116). Adah while in her subconscious state after she is operated upon in the hospital for child birth, still hears her husband's constant rebuke of her being punished for not waiting to listen to the readings of Jehovah Witness booklet, "The truth shall set you free (P. 117). Francis expects that Adah should not complain about his affair with Trudy, the so-called children nursing mother who has a foster home where their children are nursed in the day time and whom Adah is paying heavily too. She is supposed to be as quiet as "a virtuous woman whose price is above rubies (P.117). Francis Obi uses religion to intimidate and molest his wife. Religion has been abused; this is evident in Daniel and Johnson (2023) update on Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels (1848) theory which views religion as a conservative element of society and the opium of the people that it has become something that installs weakness and suppression to foster unrealistic contentment and oppression on humanity.

By adding pain to injury, Francis excuses himself to sleep with other women as he cunningly puts it," in our society men are allowed to sleep around when they want their wives to nurse a baby before another pregnancy (P.70). As a woman, Adah is expected to be subservient and docile. At 21 years of age Adah has already given birth to three children.

During Adah's third childbirth a lump sum is sent for her welfare from the Finchley Library where she works. Francis is excited that he would use 40 pounds out of the money to register a course in accounting. He is not bothered neither about his wife's needs nor her health and the hospital bills. Adah objects that she needs to buy a night dress and pay the bills. Francis queries thus, supposed this money has not arrived, what would you have bought the night dress with? (P.134). This is indeed the highest level of man's inhumanity to man.

Parental Interference in Marriage

Adah experiences isolation and negligence from her family since she refuses to marry the type of husband they want. Adah's mother and the rest of her family expect her to marry one of the old rich men that asked for her hand in marriage except her father, Pa. After Pa's death she is left alone to marry Francis who cannot afford 500 pounds bride price for a college-trained. Even though none of them contributed to her education, she was given scholarship by her hard work P. 25. Consequently, they refuse to attend her wedding and the matter becomes aggravated as her mother, Ma dies immediately she gives birth to Titi, her first child while still in the hospital. Nobody visits her to see the baby, even Boy, her only brother. She feels cheated since none of her parents are alive to see her child. Besides none of them have benefitted from her financially except her husband's people whom she has brought joy to because of her financial assistance to them.

Adah's father-in law uses hate speech to deceive her into believing that her people do not love her, with the evidence that they did not attend her wedding and did not visit her when she gave birth. She only discovers this in a painful season when her mother that she neglects is already dead. Her father-in-law tempers with her intelligence and dignity as a woman. Francis beats Adah mercilessly concerning birth control after which he writes a letter to his parents to report the matter and they both conclude that Adah is planning to get an opportunity to have affair with other men. Her health and wellbeing do not matter to them; all they want is to have children born in the homestead whether dead or alive.

Society Stratification, Social Constraints and Customs

The European society (London) at that time, and even in recent times, considers Africans as second class citizens who should not live in good houses but ghettos and keep all their children in white's foster homes where they would pay heavily to the owners of these so-called nursing homes. Africans staying in London were denied of the joy of having their children in their homes during the day time as they make sure the

children did not have an environment to play. Francis Obi who also is discriminated upon as a second class citizen by the whites has the guts to do same to his wife. Just like the African society looks at a woman as a second class citizen, Francis uses Adah's money to pay school fees but feels that as a woman she is not supposed to further her studies. She is to stay at home to cook for him, bath his babies, wash his clothes, endure his beatings, listen to his sermons, be submissive to him without complaint (P.116). Francis maintains that his family would use neither radio nor television, they would never read newspapers since it is a waste of money. Francis Obi frequently goes downstairs to Mrs. Nobles to watch their television, while Adah is banned from watching television with the excuse that Mrs. Nobles would be a bad influence on her (P.104). Adah being considered a second class citizen is not supposed to watch television; all she is expected to do is to sit down and hear from Francis "the announcing of Jehovah's Kingdom". Her first script for a novel is burnt by the husband because she is a second class citizen.

Adah is engulfed with terrible fear when her only son, Vicky is in a serious health condition in the hospital after being diagnosed of "viral meningitis". She is haunted by the fear - if Vicky should die since he is the strong bond that holds her marriage - her marriage with Francis would not be worthwhile without a boy-child. In Igbo society if you give birth to a girl it is counted as one child while a boy is counted as four children. By her reaction, the white nurse asks whether Vicky is the only child she has. Adah replies that "there is another one but she is only a girl". The white nurse does not understand the thought and the background from where the statement is derived and rebukes her. "Only a girl? What do you mean by only a girl?," She is a person too you know, just like your son (P. 68).

Based on their tradition, Adah knows that if her son gets university education, she (Adah) would be given the status of a man in the tribe (P.68). By implication, we live in a society where a woman can only be elevated by her son's achievements; it does not matter whether she is an achiever herself.

Dehumanization and Sudden Death

Based on the Igbo's culture and custom, Adah's mother, Ma is inherited by Pa's brother since the demise of her husband. She is deprived of her right to live a life of her choice. As a child, Adah feels that her mother is a disappointment to her late father by accepting to marry her husband's elder brother. Ma suffers humiliation, frustration, dehumanization and depression in the late husband brother's house which leads to her sudden death at the young age of 38. This is a clear indication of how young African women are inherited as property by their husbands' people and how they are made to suffer and die in marriage due to frustration, sexual molestation and dehumanization from so-called husbands without any penalty melted out to causative agents.

Educational Implications of Buchi Emecheta's *Second Class Citizen* on African Patriarchal System

The novel "Second Class Citizen" by Buchi Emecheta unveils the functional role of education for the African woman. This is clearly shown in the character of Adah where the novelist demonstrates the protagonist's struggle to attain education challenging the cultural, patriarchal and racial oppressive forces that deny the African woman's right to have chance of proper education. It is indeed through this novel that, one is convinced in the contemporary African society that the role of education in empowering the African woman intellectually and economically ought to be taken seriously hence it is significant to the development of society.

Furthermore, the novel exposes readers to how education has paramount significance in emancipating the African woman from subjugation, dehumanization and oppression. It is through this novel that, girl child education is acknowledged as a good thing. This is seen through Adah's education which enables her to eventually achieve her dream of being a promising writer and a successful mother. This implies that, African female writers should be given opportunities for their voices to be heard and for people to realize there is more to fiction than just the words in print.

In the novel "Second Class Citizen" people often consider education as a mere stepping stone to good credentials and economic security. However, the novel shows to readers that when people take formal and informal education seriously as a life-long project, they are bound to attain fulfillment and happiness that goes beyond mere economic security.

Conclusion

The African culture and tradition which place much emphasis on the patriarchal system is totally against God's purpose for creation of human beings in His image. According to King (2004, Genesis 1 : 27, p.3) "So God created man in his own image, in the image of God created he him; male and female created he them" Thus, any society that neglects women will surely lack in values such as equality, integrity, effective education, political and economic advancement. In other words, it is likely to experience stagnancy since a significant portion of the society cannot thrive without women emancipation. It then means women should be given equal opportunity like their men counterparts in all fields of human endeavors. The following are the recommendations

1. The emancipation of women is largely dependent on their life decisions and their level of education. Therefore, African women should be given equal rights just like their male counterparts to acquire education at any level.
2. The African women should be encouraged to have foresight, knowledgeable and demonstrate hard work which could be the only weapons for liberation of womanhood. This is because they have the

ample chance to make their dreams come true only when they realize themselves as the strong force of the society.

3. Women's active roles in politics may pave way for emancipation, especially when they are involved in policy formulation, decision making while in leadership positions where they could influence societal rules, norms and regulations.
4. The African men and women should imbibe the spirit of self esteem, consciousness of the dignity of women and human rights. This is what every woman and man need to enforce in order to live a good life.

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